

S5p+I - SO₂ LH PUM

document number : S5P+I-SO2LH-D7-PUM-v1
authors : Pascal Hedelt
CI identification : *None*
issue : 1.0
date : 2021-09-24
status : Final

Document approval record

	digital signature
Prepared:	
Checked:	

Document change record

issue	date	item	comments
0.9	2021-07-16	All	Initial version
0.9.1	2021-08-30	Section 6.4	Added time_utc variable
		Chapter 7	Added sulfurdioxide_total_vertical_column_threshold global attribute
		Sections 7.1	Updated description of qa_value variable
			Added layer dimension
		Sections 7.1.2	Added time_utc variable
			Updated number_of_processed_pixels variable name and description
			Added sulfurdioxide_profile and height_grid variables
0.9.2	2021-09-16	Section 7.1	Updated description of qa_value variable
1.0.0	2021-09-24		Final

Contents

Document approval record	2
Document change record	3
List of Tables	4
1 Introduction	5
1.1 Identification	5
1.2 Purpose and objective	5
1.3 Document overview	5
2 Applicable and reference documents	6
2.1 Applicable documents	6
2.2 Standard documents	6
2.3 Reference documents	6
2.4 Electronic references	6
3 Acronyms, terms and Definitions	7
3.1 Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms	7
4 File name convention	7
5 S5p/TROPOMI L2 Sulphur Dioxide Layer Height (SO₂ LH) Product Description	7
6 Structure of the S5P/TROPOMI SO₂ LH Level 2 file	8
6.1 S5p/TROPOMI SO ₂ LH L2 File Format	8
6.2 Dimensions and dimension ordering	9
6.3 Geolocation and pixel corners	9
6.4 Time information	9
7 Description of the SO₂ LH product	10
7.1 Group "PRODUCT"	10
7.1.1 Group "GEOLOCATIONS" in "PRODUCT/SUPPORT_DATA"	13
7.1.2 Group "DETAILED_RESULTS" in "PRODUCT/SUPPORT_DATA"	14
7.1.3 Group "INPUT_DATA" in "PRODUCT/SUPPORT_DATA"	16
7.2 References	19

List of Tables

1 Components of the S5P SO ₂ LH L2 product file name.	7
---	---

1 Introduction

1.1 Identification

This document is identified as S5P+I-SO2LH-D7-PUM-v1. It describes the technical characteristics of the S5p/TROPOMI S5P+I SO₂ Layer Height Level 2 product (hereafter referred to as SO₂ LH L2) that are needed for efficient and correct use of the data contained.

1.2 Purpose and objective

This Product User Manual (PUM) describes the technical characteristics of the S5p/TROPOMI SO₂ LH L2 geophysical data product that is needed for efficient and correct use of the data contained. A description of the related retrieval SO₂ layer height algorithm can be found in [RD1]. In this PUM the structure of the L2 datafile is described. Note that the SO₂ LH L2 datafile follows the structure of the S5p/TROPOMI L2 products. The S5P SO₂ LH algorithm uses as input the S5P SO₂ L2 product, hence several fields are copied from this product (see [RD2]).

1.3 Document overview

First, the file name convention of the SO₂ LH L2 file is described in Sect. 4. Section 5 describes the SO₂ LH data product with information about the use of the data. Format and L2 structure and are addressed in Sect. 6 followed by the detailed description of the SO₂ LH data.

2 Applicable and reference documents

2.1 Applicable documents

There are no applicable documents

2.2 Standard documents

[SD1] Space Engineering – Software.
source: ESA/ECSS; **ref:** ECSS-E-ST-40C; **date:** 2009-03-06.

2.3 Reference documents

- [RD1] S5P+I: SO₂ LH Algorithm Theoretical Baseline Document.
source: DLR; **ref:** S5P+I-SO2LH-D4-ATBD; **issue:** 4.0; **date:** 2021-07-15.
- [RD2] Sentinel-5 Precursor/TROPOMI Level 2 Product User Manual SO₂ Total Column.
source: DLR; **ref:** S5P-DLR-L2-PUM-400E; **issue:** 2.1.0; **date:** 2020-02-28.
- [RD3] Tailoring of the Earth Observation File Format Standard for the Sentinel 5 precursor Ground Segment.
source: ESA/ESTEC; **ref:** S5P-TN-ESA-GS-106; **issue:** 2.2; **date:** 2015-02-20.
- [RD4] Algorithm theoretical basis document for the TROPOMI L01b data processor.
source: KNMI; **ref:** S5P-KNMI-L01B-0009-SD; **issue:** 8.0.0; **date:** 2017-06-01.
- [RD5] Data elements and interchange formats – Information interchange – Representation of dates and times.
source: ISO; **ref:** ISO 8601:2004(E); **issue:** 3; **date:** 2004-12-01.

2.4 Electronic references

- [ER1] Unidata; *NetCDF library and documentation*. URL <http://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/>.
- [ER2] NetCDF Users Guide (2011). URL <http://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/docs/netcdf.html>.
- [ER3] Brian Eaton, Jonathan Gregory, Bob Drach *et al.*; *NetCDF Climate and Forecast (CF) Metadata Conventions*. Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (2014). Version 1.7 draft; URL <http://cfconventions.org>.

3 Acronyms, terms and Definitions

3.1 Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

ATBD	Algorithm Theoretical Baseline Document
CF	Climate and Forecast metadata conventions [ER1]
FP_ILM	Full Physics Inverse Learning Machine
LH	Layer Height
NUG	netCDF-4 Users Guide [ER2]
NRT	Near real time
PUM	Product User Manual
S5P	Sentinel-5 Precursor
SO ₂	Sulfur dioxide
TROPOMI	Tropospheric Ozone Measurement Instrument
VCD	Vertical column density

4 File name convention

The filename follows the filename conventions of all the S5p products, which is detailed in [RD3] (cf. chapter 4 therein). An example of the full real name is as following:

S5P_NRTI_L2__SO2LH__20190622T000000_20190622T000000_09245_040000_20210716T173511.nc

The components of this file name are given in Tab. 1. Components are separated by underscores, except for the file extension at the end, which is separated by a period. Character indices start counting at 0, the end-index is a Python style index, it lists the first character not in the block.

Start	End	Length	Meaning
0	3	3	Mission name
4	8	4	Processing stream, one of “NRTI” (near real-time), “OFFL” (offline) or “RPRO” (reprocessing)
9	19	10	Product identifier
20	35	15	Start of granule in UTC as “YYYYMMDDTHHMMSS”. The “T” is a fixed character.
36	51	15	End of the granule in UTC as “YYYYMMDDTHHMMSS”. The “T” is a fixed character.
52	57	5	Orbit number
59	65	6	Processor version number as “MMmmp”, with “MM” the major version number, “mm” the minor version number, and “pp” the patch level.
66	81	15	The time of processing for this granule in UTC as “YYYYMMDDTHHMMSS”. The “T” is a fixed character.
82	84	2	The file name extension. All SO ₂ LH L2 files are netCDF-4 files and use the extension “nc”.

Table 1: Components of the S5P SO₂ LH L2 product file name.

5 S5p/TROPOMI L2 Sulphur Dioxide Layer Height (SO₂ LH) Product Description

The ‘Full-Physics Inverse Learning Machine’ (hereafter referred to as FP_ILM) for the retrieval of the SO₂ layer height is based on [Hedelt et al., 2019] which was developed for the retrieval of the SO₂ LH based on TROPOMI data. It was further optimized in the framework of this ESA Sentinel-5p Innovations project.

Conceptually, the FP_ILM consists of a training phase, in which the inversion operator is trained using synthetic data generated with an appropriate radiative transfer model (RTM), and an operational phase, in which the inversion operator is applied to real satellite measurements. The main advantage of the FP_ILM over classical direct fitting approaches is that the time-consuming training phase involving complex RT modeling is performed offline; the inverse operator itself is robust and computationally simple and therefore extremely fast.

During the training phase, the Linearized Discrete Ordinate Radiative Transfer model (LIDORT) with inelastic rotational Raman scattering (RRS) implementation [Spurr et al., 2008] is deployed to compute simulated reflectance spectra in the wavelength range 311–335 nm, which are then convolved with the TROPOMI Instrument Spectral Response Function (ISRF). To extract the information about the layer height and to reduce the dimensionality of the spectral dataset, a principal component analysis (PCA) is applied to the simulated spectra, which also include noise. By thus characterizing the set of simulated measurements with fewer parameters, a simpler, more stable and computationally efficient inversion scheme can be realized.

The dimensionality-reduced spectra, together with information about the O₃ VCD, the viewing angles, the surface pressure and albedo of each training data-point, are then used as input to train a feedforward artificial neural network including regression, with the corresponding SO₂ LH as the output layer.

In the operational phase, the first step is to use the principal component scores acquired during the training phase to transform a given TROPOMI spectral measurement data set to one with a lower dimension. Once this is done, the neural network inverse function is then applied to retrieve the SO₂ LH.

A detailed algorithm description can be found in the SO₂ LH Algorithm Theoretical Baseline Document (ATBD) [RD1].

6 Structure of the S5P/TROPOMI SO₂ LH Level 2 file

The outermost layer is the file itself. Within the file there is the group “PRODUCT” which contains sub-groups to organise the data and make it easier to find what you are looking for.

PRODUCT This group stores the main data fields of the SO₂ LH product, including the precision of the main parameter, latitude, longitude and variable to determine the observation time and the dimensions needed for the data ,i.e. a time reference dimension (time), the number of measurements in the granule (scanline), the number of spectra in a measurement (ground_pixel). The “qa_value” parameter summarizes the processing flags into a continuous value, giving a quality percentage: 100% is the most optimal value, 0% is a processing failure, in between lies a continuum of values.

In the "PRODUCT" group a sub-group "SUPPORT_DATA" can be found:

SUPPORT_DATA Additional data that is not directly needed for using and understanding the main data product is stored in sub-groups of this group.

The data in this group is further split up into the following sub groups:

GEOLOCATIONS Additional geolocation and geometry related fields, including the pixel boundaries (pixel corners), viewing- and solar zenith angles, azimuth angles.

DETAILED_RESULTS Additional output that are not the main parameters, output describing the quality of the retrieval result, such as a detailed processing flags.

INPUT_DATA Additional input data, such as meteorological input data, surface albedo values, surface altitude and other data that was used to derive the output.

6.1 S5p/TROPOMI SO₂ LH L2 File Format

The file format used for the SO₂ LH L2 product (as well as all S5p/TROPOMI L2 products) is netCDF-4 [ER1]. This file format is very versatile and flexible and will be used for other Sentinel missions, e.g. Sentinel 4 mission, as well as other ESA and NASA missions.

The NetCDF-4 library is built on top of NetCDF-3 and HDF-5 libraries and it allows a grouping mechanism as well as a wide collection of datatypes and other features tailored from the HDF-5 library. This permits the user to use either the netCDF-4 or HDF-5 APIs in order to read the data. Those APIs are written in many data-analysis packages such as IDL, NCO, Matlab, R, and Mathematica or in general programming languages including Python, Ruby, C, C++, Java and Fortran 90.

6.2 Dimensions and dimension ordering

All variables in a NetCDF-4 file use named and shared dimensions. This explicitly connects variables to dimensions, and to each other.

time A time dimension. The length of this dimension is 1. The reason this dimension is used are compatibility with Level 1B, and forward compatibility with Sentinel 4 and Level 3 output.

scanline The dimension that indicates the flight direction.

ground_pixel The dimension perpendicular to the flight direction.

The climate and forecast metadata conventions recommend a specific order for dimensions in a variable [ER3] (cf. Sect. 2.4 therein). Spatiotemporal dimensions should appear in the relative order: “date or time” (*T*) “latitude” (*Y*), and “longitude” (*X*). Note that the ordering of the dimensions is row-major: the last dimension is stored contiguously in memory.

The S5P/TROPOMI Level 1B/Level 2 observation grid is not a regular grid. Because of the polar orbit, the across track dimension (‘ground_pixel’) corresponds most closely with the longitude, and therefore is associated with the X-dimension, while the along track dimensions (‘scanline’) corresponds most directly with latitude, and is therefore labelled as the Y-dimension.

6.3 Geolocation and pixel corners

The latitude, longitude, pixel corner coordinates and related angles and satellite position in the SO₂ LH L2 file are copied from the level 1B input data [RD4] (cf. chapters 26 and 27). Details about the definitions can be found there. Note that the latitude and longitude have not been corrected for the local surface altitude, but are instead given at the intersection of the line of sight with the WGS84 ellipsoid.

The geo-coordinates of the pixel corners are shown in Fig. 1 and follow the CF metadata standard [ER3] (cf. Sect. 7.1 therein).

Figure 1: Pixel corner coordinates following CF-metadata.

6.4 Time information

Time information is stored in two steps: The time dimension indicates the reference time. This reference time is defined to be UTC midnight before the start of the orbit, which itself is defined by spacecraft midnight. The `time` variable contains the reference time in seconds since 2010-01-01, UTC midnight. The offset of individual measurements within the granule/orbit is given in milliseconds with respect to this reference time in the variable `delta_time`.

The reason for this double reference is to more closely follow the CF conventions. Because the flight direction relates the latitude and the time within the orbit, we have Y and T dimensions that are closely related. By separating these into a time dimension of length 1 and a scanline dimension, we obtain independent Y and T dimensions. The actual observation time of an individual observation must be reconstructed from an offset and a time-delta.

The time is also stored in the 'time_julian' variable, which is a float array with each observation time stored as a Julian Date (as used in astronomy). This is the reference time system as used in IDL. Furthermore, the time is stored in the 'time_utc' variable, which is a string array with each observation time stored as an ISO date string.

7 Description of the SO₂ LH product

Description of the main output file of the SO₂ LH L2 product from the TROPOMI instrument on the Sentinel 5-precursor mission. An SO₂ LH L2 product is only generated for orbits or NRT granules for which the SO₂ LH retrievals was triggered, i.e. when it includes substantial amounts of SO₂. Only the pixels for which the LH retrieval was triggered contain data. All other pixels contain fill-values.

Global attributes

<i>Name</i>	<i>Value</i>	<i>Type</i>
Conventions	'CF-1.7' (static)	NC_STRING
Name of the conventions followed by the dataset. This attribute originates from the NUG standard.		
institution	'DLR' (static)	NC_STRING
The institute where the original data was produced. This attribute originates from the NUG standard.		
source	'Sentinel 5 precursor, TROPOMI, space-borne remote sensing, L2' (static)	NC_STRING
Method of production of the original data. Value includes instrument, generic description of retrieval, product level, and adds a short product name and processor version. This attribute originates from the CF standard.		
orbit	0 (dynamic)	NC_INT
The absolute orbit number, starting at 1 – first ascending node crossing after spacecraft separation.		
project	'S5P+I: SO2LH' (static)	NC_STRING
The name of the scientific project that created the data. This attribute originates from the CCI standard.		
platform	'S5P' (static)	NC_STRING
Name of the satellite, set to "S5P". This attribute originates from the CCI standard.		
sensor	'TROPOMI' (static)	NC_STRING
Name of the sensor, set to "TROPOMI". This attribute originates from the CCI standard.		
algorithm_version	'4.0.0' (dynamic)	NC_STRING
The algorithm version, separate from the processor (framework) version, to accommodate different release schedules.		
spatial_resolution	'5.5 x 3.6 km ² ' (static)	NC_STRING
Spatial resolution at nadir. This attribute originates from the CCI standard.		
sulfurdioxide_- vertical_column_- threshold	'15 DU' (static)	NC_STRING
Minimum SO ₂ vertical column density needed to trigger the product generation.		

7.1 Group "PRODUCT"

This is the main group containing the SO₂ LH product. At this level the dimensions are defined, the actual data can be found one level deeper.

The dimensions are located in the "PRODUCT" group, and can be accessed from that group and all

sub-groups of the “PRODUCT” group. All dimensions have an associated variable. These variables give a meaning to the dimension, spanning the axis of other variables.

Dimensions in “PRODUCT” group

scanline The number of measurements along the swath, in the flight-direction.

size: unlimited

source: L1B

ground_pixel The number of ground pixels across track. This depends on the product and will follow the dimension found in the input Level 1B product.

size: -1 (dynamic)

source: L1B

time The time dimension

size: 1 (fixed)

corner The number of corners for a pixel.

size: 4 (fixed)

layer The number of layers in the SO₂ profile data.

size: 1 (dynamic)

Variables in “PRODUCT” group

scanline

Description: The coordinate variable `scanline` refers to the along-track dimension of the measurement. The scanlines are time-ordered, meaning that “earlier” measurements have a lower index than “later” measurements. This variable merely contains an index to ensure that when indicating a pixel in a file the same index is used.

Dimensions: `scanline` (coordinate variable)

Type: NC_INT

Source: Processor

Unit: Dimensionless, no physical quantity.

Axis: ‘Y’ (static)

ground_pixel

Description: The coordinate variable `ground_pixel` refers to the across-track dimension of the measurement. The `ground_pixel` ordering is from left to right with respect to the flight direction, i.e. west to east during the ascending part of the orbit, i.e. a higher index corresponds to a higher longitude. This variable merely contains an index to ensure that when indicating a pixel in a file the same index is used.

Dimensions: `ground_pixel` (coordinate variable)

Type: NC_INT

Source: Processor

Unit: Dimensionless, no physical quantity.

Axis: ‘X’ (static)

time

Description: The variable `time(time)` is the reference time of the measurements. The reference time is set to YYYY-MM-DDT00:00:00 UTC, midnight UTC before spacecraft midnight, the formal start of the current orbit. The `delta_time(scanline)` variable indicates the time difference of the observations with the reference time. Thus combining the information of `time(time)` and `delta_time(scanline)` yields the measurement time for each scanline as UTC time.

Dimensions: time
Type: NC_INT
Source: Processor
Unit: 'seconds since 2010-01-01 00:00:00' (static)
Axis: 'T' (static)

delta_time

Description: The `delta_time(scanline)` variable indicates the time difference with the reference time `time(time)`. Thus combining the information of `time(time)` and `delta_time(scanline)` yields the start of the measurement time for each scanline. Note that one scanline measurement is the result of adding independent measurements during one coaddition period, hence the `delta_time` for each ground pixel in a scanline is identical.

This variable gives the time offset in ms accuracy

Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel
Type: NC_FLOAT
Source: Processor
Unit: 'milliseconds since time' (static)

time_julian

Description: The time of observation expressed as Julian date (cf. ISO 8601 [RD5]). Julian dates are expressed as a Julian day number (i.e. the continuous count of days since the beginning of the Julian period) plus the decimal fraction of a day since the preceding noon in Universal Time. It is used primarily by astronomers and in software for easily calculating the elapsed time between two events.

Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel
Type: NC_FLOAT
Source: Processor
Unit: 'milliseconds' (static)

time_utc

Description: The time of observation expressed as ISO 8601 [RD5] date string.

Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel
Type: NC_STRING
Source: Processor

latitude

Description: The latitude of the pixel centers of the ground pixels in the data. Latitude, longitude coordinates for the ground pixel center and the ground pixel corners are calculated at the WGS84 ellipsoid.

Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: Processor.
Unit: 'degrees_north' (static)

longitude

Description: The longitude of the pixel centers of the ground pixels in the data. Latitude, longitude coordinates for the ground pixel center and the ground pixel corners are calculated at the WGS84 ellipsoid.

Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: Processor.
Unit: 'degrees_east' (static)

qa_value

Description: A continuous quality descriptor, varying between 0 (no data) and 1 (full quality data). Initially, the *qa_value* has a value of unity (i.e. 1) for each pixel for which the LH retrieval is triggered, otherwise 0. There are currently two conditions that are formulated consecutively and that, once met, decrease the *qa_value* by 25% ($qa_value = qa_value * 0.75$) of the previous value:

1. When one of the retrieval input parameters exceeds the training data range.
2. When the optimized SO₂ VCD (calculated using the retrieved LH) $VCD_{opt} < 20$ DU.

If the retrieved SO₂ LH < 0 km or the optimized SO₂ $VCD_{opt} < 15$ DU the value is set to 0 and the corresponding output parameters are set to NaN. It is recommended to ignore data with $qa_value < 0.5$

Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT
Source: Processor
Unit: Dimensionless, no physical quantity.

sulfurdioxide_layer_mid_height

Description: Height at center of the SO₂ layer w.r.t. the sea level.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: Processor.
Unit: 'm' (static)

sulfurdioxide_layer_mid_height_precision

Description: Error of the height at center of the SO₂ layer.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: Processor.
Unit: 'm' (static)

7.1.1 Group “GEOLOCATIONS” in “PRODUCT/SUPPORT_DATA”

Variables in “PRODUCT/SUPPORT_DATA/GEOLOCATIONS”

solar_zenith_angle

Description: Solar zenith angle θ_0 (SZA) at the ground pixel location on the reference ellipsoid. Angle is measured away from the vertical. ESA definition of day side: $\theta_0 < 92^\circ$.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: Processor.
Unit: 'degree' (static)

viewing_zenith_angle

Description: Viewing zenith angle θ (VZA) at the ground pixel location on the reference ellipsoid. Angle is measured away from the vertical.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: Processor.
Unit: 'degree' (static)

relative_azimuth_angle

Description: Relative azimuth angle ϕ_0 (RAA) between the SZA θ_0 and VZA θ .
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.

Source: Processor.
Unit: 'degree' (static)

latitude_bounds

Description: The latitude of the pixel corners of the ground pixels in the data. Latitude, longitude coordinates for the ground pixel center and the ground pixel corners are calculated at the WGS84 ellipsoid.
The order of the pixel corners follows the CF-metadata conventions [ER3] (cf. Sect. 7.1 therein), i.e. the ordering is counter-clockwise when viewed from above.

Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: Processor.
Unit: 'degrees_north' (static)

longitude_bounds

Description: The longitude of the pixel corners of the ground pixels in the data. Latitude, longitude coordinates for the ground pixel center and the ground pixel corners are calculated at the WGS84 ellipsoid.
The order of the pixel corners follows the CF-metadata conventions [ER3] (cf. Sect. 7.1 therein), i.e. the ordering is counter-clockwise when viewed from above.

Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: Processor.
Unit: 'degrees_east' (static)

7.1.2 Group “DETAILED_RESULTS” in “PRODUCT/SUPPORT_DATA”

Dimensions in “PRODUCT/SUPPORT_DATA/DETAILED_RESULTS”

number_of_processed_pixels Number of pixels fulfilling the SO₂ threshold criterion see also 'sulfurdioxide_vertical_column_threshold' global attribute) and for which the SO₂ LH retrieval was triggered.

size: -1 (dynamic)

Variables in “PRODUCT/SUPPORT_DATA/DETAILED_RESULTS”

number_of_processed_pixels

Description: Absolute number of pixels for this NRT granule or OFFL orbit, for which the SO₂ LH retrieval was triggered.

Dimensions: number_of_processed_pixels.
Type: NC_INT.
Source: Processor.
Unit: Dimensionless, no physical quantity.

sulfurdioxide_layer_top_height

Description: Bottom height of the SO₂ layer w.r.t. the sea level. The top height was calculated from the LH mid height by adding a value of 1.250 m (i.e. the HWHM of the a priori SO₂ profile).

Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: Processor.
Unit: 'm' (static)

sulfurdioxide_layer_bottom_height

Description: Top height of the SO₂ layer w.r.t. the sea level. The top height was calculated from the LH mid height by subtracting a value of 1.250 m (i.e. the HWHM of the a priori SO₂ profile).

Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.

Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: Processor.
Unit: 'm' (static)

sulfurdioxide_layer_mid_pressure

Description: Pressure of the SO₂ layer center.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: Processor.
Unit: 'Pa' (static)

sulfurdioxide_layer_top_pressure

Description: Pressure of the SO₂ layer top.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: Processor.
Unit: 'Pa' (static)

sulfurdioxide_layer_bottom_pressure

Description: Pressure of the SO₂ layer bottom.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: Processor.
Unit: 'Pa' (static)

sulfurdioxide_layer_height_flag

Description: Processing flag indicating warnings and errors during the SO₂ LH retrieval. Note that the flag value adds up in case of different warnings/errors occurring, according to the following list:

- 0: No errors or warning in the retrieval
- 1: One of the L2 input parameters exceeds the trained data range (input limit warning).
- 2: Retrieved SO₂ LH exceeds trained output datarange (i.e. 0.5 – 25 km) (output limit warning).
- 4: Aerosol absorption index $AAI \geq 2$ (absorbing ash present warning).
- 8: Aerosol absorption index $AAI < 0$ (non-absorbing sulfate aerosol present warning).
- 16: SO₂ VCD calculated at retrieved SO₂ LH $VCD \leq 15DU$ (optimized VCD below threshold error).
- 32: SO₂ LH < 0 m (LH below 0 m error).

For pixels for which no SO₂ LH retrieval the variable is set to NaN.

With this flag, the user can easily set-up his own filter. For example, a very conservative user might only use pixels with $flag == 0$, whereas for the common user a threshold filter value of $flag < 16$ is suggested.

Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: Processor.
Unit: '1' (static)

sulfurdioxide_total_vertical_column_optimized

Description: Vertical column density of SO₂ calculated at the corresponding SO₂ LH.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.

Source: Processor.
Unit: 'mol m-2' (static)

sulfurdioxide_total_air_mass_factor_layer

Description: Total air mass factor calculated for the SO₂ LH.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: Processor.
Unit: '1' (static)

sulfurdioxide_profile

Description: Volume mixing ratio profile of SO₂.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel, layer.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: Processor.
Unit: 'mol m-2' (static)

height_grid

Description: Height grid for the SO₂ profile.
Dimensions: layer.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: Processor.
Unit: 'm' (static)

7.1.3 Group "INPUT_DATA" in "PRODUCT/SUPPORT_DATA"

Variables in "PRODUCT/SUPPORT_DATA/INPUT_DATA"

sulfurdioxide_detection_flag

Description: Pixel-wise flag which indicates if enhanced SO₂ has been detected from a potential volcanic eruption. The flag is 0 for no detection, 1 for SO₂ detection, 2 for clear volcanic detection, 3 for detection close to known anthropogenic source, 4 for detection at high SZA (potential false-positive).
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_INT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product.
Unit: '1' (static)

surface_albedo_328nm

Description: Surface albedo from OMI database at 328nm.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product.
Unit: '1' (static)

surface_pressure

Description: Surface pressure from ECMWF model data.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product.
Unit: 'Pa' (static)

surface_altitude

Description: The mean of the sub-pixels of the surface altitude above the reference geoid (WGS84) within the approximate field of view, based on the GMTED2010 surface elevation database.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.

Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product.
Unit: 'm' (static)

cloud_fraction_crb

Description: Retrieved effective radiometric cloud fraction using the OCRA/ROCINN CRB model.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product.
Unit: '1' (static)

cloud_pressure_crb

Description: Retrieved atmospheric pressure at the level of cloud using the OCRA/ROCINN CRB model.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product.
Unit: 'Pa' (static)

cloud_pressure_crb

Description: Retrieved atmospheric pressure at the level of cloud using the OCRA/ROCINN CRB model.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product.
Unit: 'Pa' (static)

cloud_albedo_crb

Description: Albedo of cloud using the OCRA/ROCINN CRB model.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product.
Unit: '1' (static)

cloud_height_crb

Description: Retrieved height at the level of cloud w.r.t. the geoid/MSL using the OCRA/ROCINN CRB model.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product.
Unit: 'm' (static)

ozone_total_vertical_column

Description: Main output data of O₃ total column product calculated with a DOAS algorithm for near real-time processing, while for offline and reprocessing the O₃ is calculated with the GODfit algorithm.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product.
Unit: 'mol m⁻²' (static)

aerosol_index_340_380

Description: Aerosol index at wavelengths 340/380 (i.e. the TOMS pair) retrieved by L2 AER_AI algorithm. This variable is a carbon copy of the variable in the L2 AER_AI L2 product and is directly read from the SO₂ L2 product.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.

Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product
Unit: '1' (static)

aerosol_mid_height

Description: Height at center of aerosol layer relative to geoid, retrieved by L2 AER_ALH algorithm. This variable is only available in case a S5P AER_ALH L2 product was available during the SO₂ LH retrieval. This variable is a carbon copy of the variable in the L2 AER_ALH product.

Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: AER_ALH L2 product
Unit: 'm' (static)

sulfurdioxide_total_vertical_column_polluted

Description: Vertical column density of the sulphur dioxide SO₂ product for the polluted scenario (anthropogenic SO₂ in the PBL).

Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product.
Unit: 'mol m-2' (static)

sulfurdioxide_total_vertical_column_15km

Description: Vertical column density of the sulfur dioxide SO₂ product for a sulfur dioxide plume at 15 km altitude w.r.t. the sea level.

Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product.
Unit: 'mol m-2' (static)

sulfurdioxide_total_vertical_column_7km

Description: Vertical column density of the sulfur dioxide SO₂ product for a sulfur dioxide plume at 7 km altitude w.r.t. the sea level.

Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product.
Unit: 'mol m-2' (static)

sulfurdioxide_total_vertical_column_1km

Description: Vertical column density of the sulfur dioxide SO₂ product for a sulfur dioxide plume at 1 km altitude w.r.t. the topography.

Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product.
Unit: 'mol m-2' (static)

sulfurdioxide_total_air_mass_factor_polluted

Description: Total air mass factor, *M* for the polluted case.

Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product.
Unit: '1' (static)

sulfurdioxide_total_air_mass_factor_15km

Description: Total air mass factor, *M* for a sulfur dioxide plume at 15 km altitude w.r.t. the sea level.

Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.

Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product.
Unit: '1' (static)

sulfurdioxide_total_air_mass_factor_7km

Description: Total air mass factor, M for a sulfur dioxide plume at 7 km altitude w.r.t. the sea level.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product.
Unit: '1' (static)

sulfurdioxide_total_air_mass_factor_1km

Description: Total air mass factor, M for a sulfur dioxide plume at 1 km altitude w.r.t. the topography.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product.
Unit: '1' (static)

sulfurdioxide_slant_column_corrected

Description: SO₂ slant column density, corrected by the background correction algorithm.
Dimensions: time, scanline, ground_pixel.
Type: NC_FLOAT.
Source: SO₂ L2 product.
Unit: '1' (static)

7.2 References

- [Hedelt et al., 2019] Hedelt, P., Efremenko, D., R., L., G., D., Spurr, R. J. D., and Clarisse, L. (2019). SO₂ Layer Height retrieval from Sentinel-5Precursor/TROPOMI using FP_ILM. *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 12(10).
- [Spurr et al., 2008] Spurr, R., de Haan, J., van Oss, R., and Vasilkov, A. (2008). Discrete-ordinate radiative transfer in a stratified medium with first-order rotational Raman scattering. *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy & Radiative Transfer*, 109:404–425.